

Studies in Chromones and Flavones. Part XI: Synthesis of Some Bichromonyls

S. P. PRAJAPATI and SURESH SETHNA

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science,
M. S. University of Baroda, Baroda.

Manuscript received 8 November 1974; revised 8 November 1975; accepted 10 November 1975.

8, 8'- and 6, 6'-bichromonyl, 8, 8'- and 6, 6'-bichromonyl methane, 6, 6'-bichromonyl ketone and 6, 6'-bichromonyl sulfone have been synthesised from 2, 2'-dihydroxy and 4, 4'-dihydroxy-biphenyl, 2, 2'- and 4, 4'-dihydroxydiphenyl methane, 4, 4'-dihydroxybenzophenone and 4, 4'-dihydroxydiphenyl sulfone respectively through cyanoethylation, hydrolysis of the cyanoethoxy derivatives obtained to the corresponding acids, cyclisation of the acids with PPA to the bichromanonyls and their dehydrogenation. Hydrolysis of the bichromonyls with alkali gave the corresponding phenolic ketones.

CYANOETHYLATION of phenols affords a convenient method for the synthesis of chromones without any substituent in the heterocyclic ring. The present work deals with the synthesis of 8, 8'- and 6, 6'-bichromonyl, 8, 8'- and 6, 6'-bichromonyl methane, 6, 6'-bichromonyl ketone and 6, 6'-bichromonyl sulfone from 2, 2'- and 4, 4'-dihydroxydiphenyl, 2, 2'- and 4, 4'-dihydroxydiphenyl methane, 4, 4'-dihydroxybenzophenone and 4, 4'-dihydroxydiphenyl sulfone respectively. These phenols have been condensed with acrylonitrile in the presence of cupric oxide which was found to give the best results except in the case of 4, 4'-dihydroxydiphenyl where sodium hydroxide gave better yield. The other catalysts tried besides these two were cuprous chloride, sodium methoxide and Triton B. The intermediate cyanoethoxy derivatives have been hydrolysed to the corresponding acids which on cyclisation with PPA afforded the bichromanonyl derivatives which on dehydrogenation with palladium on charcoal gave the bichromonyl derivatives. The bichromonyls on hydrolysis with alkali gave the corresponding phenolic ketones which are known except 2, 2'-dihydroxy-3, 3'-diacetyldiphenyl and 2, 2'-dihydroxy-3, 3'-diacetyldiphenyl methane obtained from 8, 8'-bichromonyl and 8, 8'-bichromonyl methane respectively which are hitherto unknown.

The I.R. spectra of the bichromanonyls, bichromonyls and the diacetyl derivatives obtained on hydrolysis showed the characteristic peak for the carbonyl group and the U.V. spectra of the bichromanonyls and bichromonyls which were taken either in dioxan or chloroform gave the characteristic λ max.²

Experimental

2, 2'-Di(β -cyanoethoxy)diphenyl: A mixture of 2, 2'-dihydroxydiphenyl (2 g.), acrylonitrile (5 ml.) and cupric oxide (0.2 g.) was refluxed for 30 hr. The

reaction mixture was extracted with chloroform and the extract was washed successively with dil. sodium hydroxide, dil. hydrochloric acid and finally with water. The product left on removal of chloroform

crystallised from alcohol in white needles (0.7 g.) m.p. 100°–101°. (Found: C, 74.13; H, 5.57; N, 9.22. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$ requires C, 74.00; H, 5.48; N, 9.59%.)

2, 2'-Di(β -carboxyethoxy)diphenyl: The above cyano derivative (1 g.) was refluxed with conc. hydrochloric acid (50 ml.) for 4 hr. The product obtained on cooling was purified through sodium bicarbonate extraction. It crystallised from dil. alcohol in light pink plates (0.5 g.), m.p. 157°–59°. (Found: C, 65.54; H, 5.24. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_6$ requires C, 65.46; H, 5.45%.)

8,8'-Bichromanonyl : The above acid (0.5 g.) was heated with PPA (20 g. P_2O_5 ; 10 ml. orthophosphoric acid) on a steam bath for 7 hr. It was then poured in ice-cold water and kept overnight. The separated product was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and crystallised from acetic acid in pale yellow needles (0.15 g.), m.p. 229°-30°. (Found : C, 73.16; H, 4.55. $C_{18}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 73.50; H, 4.76%). I.R. 1680 cm^{-1} ($>C=O$). U.V. λ_{max} 252 and 328 nm.

8,8'-Bichromonyl (I) : A mixture of 8,8'-bichromanonyl (0.5 g.) in diphenyl ether (5 ml.) and Pd/C (10%; 0.25 g.) was refluxed for 7 hr. and filtered hot. The product obtained on cooling crystallised from glacial acetic acid in shining needles (0.2 g.), m.p. 326°. (Found : C, 74.69; H, 3.81. $C_{18}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 74.50; H, 3.45%). I.R. 1640 cm^{-1} ($>C=O$). U.V. λ_{max} 251 and 306 nm.

2,2'-Dihydroxy-3,3'-diacetyldiphenyl : 8,8'-Bichromonyl (50 mg.) was refluxed with sodium hydroxide (10 ml.; 10%) for 20 min. The product obtained on acidification of the alkaline solution crystallised from alcohol in pale yellow needles, m.p. 167°-68°. (2,4-DNP—m.p. 302°-303°). It gave a violet colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found : C, 71.14; H, 4.81. $C_{18}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 71.10; H, 5.18%). I.R. 1630 cm^{-1} ($>C=O$) (s), 3300 cm^{-1} (OH bonded) (b).

4,4'-Di(β -cyanoethoxy)diphenyl : Prepared from 4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyl (2 g.), acrylonitrile (10 ml.) and sodium hydroxide (2 ml.; 10%) as before. Yellowish brown plates (0.8 g.) from alcohol. M.p. 180°-81°. (Found : C, 73.60; H, 5.32; N, 9.20. $C_{18}H_{16}N_2O_2$ requires C, 74.00; H, 5.48; N, 9.59%). Mixed m.p. with the compound prepared according to Cook and Reed³ using sodium methoxide as the catalyst was not depressed.

4,4'-Di(β -carboxyethoxy)diphenyl : Obtained by refluxing the above cyano derivative (1 g.) in acetic acid (25 ml.) with conc. hydrochloric acid (20 ml.) for 7 hr. and crystallised from glacial acetic acid in silky grey plates (0.4 g.), m.p. 241°-42°. (Found : C, 65.86; H, 5.33. $C_{18}H_{18}O_6$ requires C, 65.46; H, 5.45%).

6,6'-Bichromanonyl : Obtained by heating the above acid (0.5 g.) with PPA as before and crystallised from glacial acetic acid in pale yellow needles (0.2 g.), m.p. 205°-06°. (Found : C, 73.07; H, 4.37. $C_{18}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 73.50; H, 4.76%). I.R. 1675 cm^{-1} ($>C=O$). U.V. λ_{max} 248, 330 nm.

6,6'-Bichromonyl (II) : Obtained by refluxing a mixture of the above bichromanonyl (0.5 g.) in diphenyl ether (5 ml.) with Pd/C (0.25 g.) for 7 hr. and crystallised from glacial acetic acid gave m.p. 298°-99° (decomp.). Yield 0.1 g. It gave light blue fluorescence with conc. sulfuric acid. (Found : C, 74.82; H, 3.06. $C_{18}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 74.50; H, 3.45%). I.R. 1645 cm^{-1} ($>C=O$) U.V. λ_{max} 250, 278, 310 nm.

On hydrolysis as before it gave 3,3'-diacetyl-4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyl. M.p. and mixed m.p. with the compound prepared according to Boon-Long⁴ was 209°-10°.

2,2'-Di(β -cyanoethoxy)diphenyl methane : Prepared from 2,2'-dihydroxydiphenyl methane (2 g.), acrylonitrile (5 ml.) and cupric oxide (0.2 g.) as before and crystallised from alcohol in pale yellow needles (2.2 g.), m.p. 146°-47°. (Found : C, 74.27; H, 5.62; N, 8.97. $C_{19}H_{18}N_2O_2$ requires C, 74.50; H, 5.88; N, 9.15%).

2,2'-Di(β -carboxyethoxy)diphenyl methane : Obtained from the above cyano derivative (1 g.) by refluxing with conc. hydrochloric acid (50 ml.) for 20 hr. and crystallised from dil. alcohol in light pink needles (0.4 g.), m.p. 170°-71°. (Found : C, 66.24; H, 5.49. $C_{19}H_{20}O_6$ requires C, 66.26; H, 5.81%).

8,8'-Bichromanonyl methane : The above acid (0.5 g.) was cyclised with PPA and crystallised from alcohol in pale yellow needles (0.15 g.), m.p. 146°-47°. (Found : C, 73.89; H, 4.88. $C_{19}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 74.01; H, 5.19%). I.R. 1685 cm^{-1} ($>C=O$). U.V. λ_{max} 254, 320 nm.

8,8'-Bichromonyl methane (III) : The above chromanone (0.5 g.) was dehydrogenated as before and the product crystallised from toluene-petroleum ether mixture in orange buds (0.2 g.), m.p. 222°-23°. (Found : C, 75.44; H, 4.01. $C_{19}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 74.99; H, 3.95%). I.R. 1630 cm^{-1} ($>C=O$). U.V. λ_{max} 242, 296 nm.

2,2'-Dihydroxy-3,3'-diacetyldiphenyl methane : The above bichromone was hydrolysed as before and the phenolic ketone obtained crystallised from dil. alcohol in pale yellow needles, m.p. 108°-09°. (2,4-DNP—m.p. 277°-78°). It gave a violet colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found : C, 72.04; H, 5.33; $C_{19}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 71.83; H, 5.55%). I.R. 1625 cm^{-1} ($>C=O$) (s) 3400 cm^{-1} (OH bonded) (b).

4,4'-Di(β -cyanoethoxy)diphenyl methane : Prepared by refluxing a mixture of 4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyl methane (2 g.), acrylonitrile (5 ml.) and cupric oxide (0.2 g.) for 30 hr. Crystallised from alcohol in white needles (2.1 g.), m.p. 115°-16°. (Found : C, 74.40; H, 5.54; N, 9.00. $C_{19}H_{18}N_2O_2$ requires C, 74.50; H, 5.88; N, 9.15%).

Holsten⁵ who prepared it using a mixture of sodium-tert-butoxide and cuprous chloride as a catalyst gave the same m.p.

4,4'-Di(β -carboxyethoxy)diphenyl methane : Obtained by heating the above cyano derivative (1 g.) with conc. hydrochloric acid (50 ml.) for 7 hr. and crystallised from dil. alcohol in white shining plates (0.5 g.), m.p. 188°-89°. (Found : C, 66.33; H, 5.53. $C_{19}H_{20}O_6$ requires C, 66.26; H, 5.81%).

6,6'-Bichromanonyl methane : The above acid (1 g.) was refluxed with thionyl chloride (3 ml.) and the acid chloride obtained was directly mixed with anhydrous aluminium chloride (2 g.) in dry nitrobenzene (5 ml.) and kept overnight. The product obtained on removal of the solvent by steam distillation crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether mixture in white buds (0.2 g.), m.p. 131°-32°. (Found : C, 73.91; H, 5.16. $C_{19}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 74.01; H, 5.19%). I.R. 1680 cm^{-1} ($>C=O$). U.V. λ_{max} 252, 324, nm.

6,6'-Bichromonyl methane (IV) : The above chromanone (0.5 g.) was dehydrogenated by Pd/C as

before and crystallised from absolute alcohol in pale brown plates (0.1 g.), m.p. 193°-94°. (Found : C, 74.80; H, 4.08. $C_{18}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 74.99; H, 3.95%). I.R. 1650 cm^{-1} ($>C=O$). U.V. λ_{max} 252, 300 nm.

On hydrolysis it gave 3,3'-diacetyl-4,4'-dihydroxy-diphenyl methane. M.p. and mixed m.p. with the compound prepared according to Prajapati and Sethna⁶ was 155°-56°.

4,4'-Di(β -cyanoethoxy)benzophenone : Prepared from 4,4'-dihydroxybenzophenone (2 g.), acrylonitrile (10 ml.) and cupric oxide (0.2 g.) and crystallised from alcohol in white shining plates (1.5 g.), m.p. 136°-37°. (Found : C, 71.06; H, 4.96; N, 9.12. $C_{19}H_{16}N_2O_3$ requires C, 71.25; H, 5.00; N, 8.75%).

4,4'-Di(β -carboxyethoxy)benzophenone : Obtained by the hydrolysis of the above cyano derivative (1 g.) with sulfuric acid (20 ml; 40%) and crystallised from dil. alcohol in white shining plates (0.5 g.), m.p. 203°-04°. (Found : C, 63.92; H, 5.00. $C_{19}H_{18}O_7$ requires C, 63.70; H, 5.03%).

6,6'-Bichromanonyl ketone : Prepared by heating the above acid (0.5 g.) with PPA as before and crystallised from alcohol in white needles (0.2 g.), m.p. 193°. (Found : C, 70.76; H, 4.48. $C_{19}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 70.80; H, 4.35%). I.R. 1690 cm^{-1} ($>C=O$). U.V. λ_{max} 246, 282 nm.

6,6'-Bichromanonyl ketone (V) : The above chromanone (0.5 g.) was dehydrogenated as before and crystallised from alcohol in white needles (0.1 g.), m.p. 249°-50°. (Found : C, 71.69; H, 3.29. $C_{19}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 71.70; H, 3.15%). I.R. 1645 cm^{-1} ($>C=O$) U.V. λ_{max} 252, 286, 296, 306 nm.

On hydrolysis it gave 3,3'-diacetyl-4,4'-dihydroxybenzophenone. M.p. and mixed m.p. with this compound prepared according to Balani and Sethna⁷ was 180°-81°.

4,4'-Di(β -cyanoethoxy)diphenyl sulfone : Prepared by refluxing a mixture of 4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyl sulfone (2 g.), acrylonitrile (10 ml.) and cupric oxide

(0.2 g.). Crystallised from alcohol in white needles (0.8 g.), m.p. 155°-56°. (Found : C, 60.53; H, 4.03; N, 7.51. $C_{18}H_{16}N_2O_4S$ requires C, 60.70; H, 4.49; N, 7.87%).

4,4'-Di(β -carboxyethoxy)diphenyl sulfone : Prepared by refluxing the above cyano derivative (1 g.) with sulfuric acid (20 ml.; 40%) for 20 min. It crystallised from dil. acetic acid in white shining needles (0.4 g.), m.p. 198°-99°. (Found : C, 55.04; H, 4.65. $C_{18}H_{18}O_6S$ requires C, 54.82; H, 4.57%).

6,6'-Bichromanonyl sulfone : Obtained by heating the above acid (0.5 g.) with PPA and crystallised from alcohol in white shining plates (0.2 g.), m.p. 177°-79°. (Found : C, 60.40; H, 3.64. $C_{18}H_{14}O_6S$ requires C, 60.34; H, 3.91%). I.R. 1690 cm^{-1} ($>C=O$). U.V. λ_{max} 246, 310 nm.

6,6'-Bichromanonyl sulfone (VI) : The above bichromanonyl sulfone (0.5 g.) was dehydrogenated as before and crystallised from xylene-petroleum ether mixture in yellowish-orange plates (0.1 g.), m.p. 266°-68°. (Found : C, 60.82; H, 3.23. $C_{18}H_{10}O_6S$ requires C, 61.03; H, 2.82%). I.R. 1630 cm^{-1} ($>C=O$). U.V. λ_{max} 246, 270, 294, 304 nm.

It gave on hydrolysis 3,3'-diacetyl-4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyl sulfone. M.p. and mixed m.p. with the compound prepared according to Kulkarni⁸ was 187°-188°.

References

1. Part X. *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 50, 326.
2. F. M. DEAN, "Naturally Occurring Oxygen Ring Compounds", Butterworths, Lond., 1963, p. 252.
3. A. H. COOK and K. J. REED, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 920.
4. N. BOON-LONG, *J. Pharm. Assoc. Siam.*, 1948, 1. *Chem. Abs.*, 1949, 43, 5017.
5. J. R. HOLSTEN, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, 26, 3607.
6. S. P. PRAJAPATI and S. SETHNA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 49, 391.
7. R. A. BALANI and S. SETHNA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 45, 390.
8. V. G. KULKARNI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 40, 808.